

Exploring and Designing Employee Training and Development Programs for SMEs in Jabodetabek and Bandung

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ABSTRACT: This study gives a general overview of the training and development programs available to SMEs in Bandung and Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, and Bekasi). The problem that SMEs in Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) and Bandung is a lack of productivity and abilities, as well as resource limitations that make the business undergo difficult times. To assure the reliability and validity of the research, a qualitative methodology is employed. To gain insight into their perceptions, experiences, and expectations regarding training and development programs, the researcher determines to conduct interviews with business owners, managers, and employees. There are suggestions and feedback from respondents regarding how to enhance training, started with available resources, time constraints, and the diverse learning preferences of the owner and employee to ensure maximum effectiveness. By implementing this type of training, SME employees can increase their skills and knowledge, boost their productivity, and ultimately contribute to the development and competitiveness of their business. Additionally, this research provides more valuable insights and strategies for SME training and development programs.

KEYWORDS: Employee training, Employee development, Small Medium Enterprise (SMEs).

1. INTRODUCTION

Training and development programs have been vital to the company over the past few decades. According to a study by Khan et al. (2014), companies with superior employee training programs can improve the job performance of their employees. According to Werner and DeSimone (2006), a training program not only promotes employee development, but also helps businesses maximize their human capital to gain a competitive advantage. Therefore, it appears that business must devise these training programs for their employees in order to improve their skills and abilities at work. Earlier research by Mubarok and Putra (2018), Elnaga and Imran (2013), Mangkunegara and Agustine (2016), and Setyawati et al. (2019) revealed that training had a marginally significant positive effect on job performance. Thus, effective training programs are required for employees to learn the knowledge, talents, and skills required to perform well on the job, which may also affect employee commitment and motivation (Meyer and Allen., 1991).

Furthermore, the researcher attempted to describe some business issue explorations. The issue includes marketing, finance, human resource, operation, and etc. The details of the issues are lack of working capital, marketing issues, limited access to financial resources, lack of technology management and expertise, low productivity, inadequate access to productive resources, including markets, technology, information, and capital, institutional and cooperative organizational structures that are still inadequate, and a lack of commercial networks. Thus, in order to answer this difficulty, the researcher attempted to propose a single solution to those problems. One way is to give training and development programs for both the owner and the employee. Training and development programs can be tailored to the needs of MSMEs.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Training

Training, work motivation, and job promotion are only a few of the human resources (HR) quality characteristics and HR management strategies that will greatly affect HR job performance, according to Noe et al. (2007). One of the core functions of human resource management is employee development through suitable training and development programs. Employee development is the process of increasing an employee's capacity and capability to match the standard performance level of the business (Elena P., 2000). Training is often divided into four categories: recognizing training needs, understanding training objectives, knowing how the training will apply to the profession, and creating training to improve abilities. Identifying training as a requirement for an organization is rarely done, and this includes defining the necessary training requirements. Asfaw, Argaw, and

Bayissa (2015). Training is commonly seen as a technique for improving a resource's unique abilities, knowledge, and talents, as well as for assisting that person in comprehending specific business concepts. When combined with other strategies, training and resource development have a direct impact on the quality of HR outcomes, which leads to improved company performance (Guest, 1997).

Employee Development Programs

Employee development, according to Kuvaas and Dysvik (2010), is a critical component in conserving and expanding the abilities, knowledge, and skills of both specific employees and the organization as a whole. Development can be divided into three categories: opportunities for professional advancement, how a company is seen in the long run, and a continual commitment to investing in staff development. Employee training and development programs are primarily concerned with the acquisition of information, skills, and practices. Training and development is actually one of the pillars of human resource management since it can improve performance at both the individual and collective levels. (2014) (Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan, and Hahim). Training and development programs are a planned technique that affects employee motivation and behavior in such a way that work performance improves, and hence organizational performance increases. Opatha (2009).

Off-The-Job Training

According to Vasanthi (2019), the definition of Off-The-Job training is education gained apart from the workplace. The workplace is reproduced for training purposes. As a result, vestibule training is another name for this practice. This type of training is generally utilized for new employees who have no prior job experience and lack the requisite skills for the role. Advantages of doing off-the-job training: Because the training will be provided by experienced teachers, the information transfer will be effective. Training sessions will be meticulously organized. Training sessions may be organized on weekends or at odd hours to avoid interfering with normal working hours. New skills can be readily transmitted due to the availability of full-time training.

On-The-Job Training

According to Vasanthi (2019), on-the-job training (OJT) refers to activities performed at a person's workplace to gain the knowledge and abilities required for workers to do a certain task within the workplace. Employees learn in an environment where they must apply the knowledge and skills they have gained through on-the-job training. The Advantages of On-the-Job Training. For starters, it is a low-cost training method for transferring existing workers' expertise to a new workforce. The training content will be tailored to each skill that has to be learned. The learners are aware of the specifics of the skill to be acquired. The trainees will feel at ease because the training will take place in a familiar workplace. A good method for vetting potential new hires. The employees will create a sense of devotion to the company. The trainees are extremely motivated. It's a diverse training method. Feedback on the trainee's performance is provided immediately.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in Bandung, West Java. According to analysts (Alshenqeeti, 2014). The researcher tried to conduct semi-structured interview. This is the most prevalent interview format used by qualitative researchers. This interview technique, like structured interviews, comprises a researcher-prepared outline of topics and questions (Stuckey, 2013). Thus, the researcher also uses quantitative methods such as questionnaire to collect the data. The questionnaire is merely one method for learning more about a study topic. As a result, it might or might not be the right tool for the job. The sort of questionnaire used in this study will be closed questions. Closed (or multiple-choice) questions require the respondent to select the response that most closely matches his or her opinion from a set of potential responses. Employee performance is the dependent variable in this study, whereas employee training and development programs are the independent variables. The questionnaire will be distributed via Google Forms and filled up by MSMEs in the Jabodetabek and Bandung areas. As previously stated, the researcher will examine the data using content analysis for the qualitative technique and will use Excel to analyze the questionnaire to supplement the results of the interview.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Individual interviews, face-to-face interviews, and face-to-face group interviews are all methods of asking questions of specific participants who are the topic of a study or research and receiving responses from those individuals. Interviews are classified into three types based on their level of structure: structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured interviews.

The researcher opted to conduct a semi-structured interview to identify and learn more about the topic being addressed. The benefits of a semi-structured interview are that the questions can be prepared ahead of time, allowing the researcher to gain more information and become more competent during the interview, and the respondent can speak freely, resulting in an exceptional data result (Kabir., 2016).

Furthermore, 9 of the 12 respondents who were owners and managers of MSMEs in the Jabodetabek and Bandung areas that the researcher successfully questioned concur that training and development programs are crucial for them. A new time is chosen for each interview. The researcher conducts the interviews after receiving the results of the Google Forms survey. Their opinions of the present training and development program they have used in the past are the main topics of the interview questions.

The researcher attempted to pinpoint the problem with training and development programs based on the answers to the aforementioned questionnaire and interview. The length of the training is the first. The majority of respondents stated that more time is required to improve training and development programs. They race to absorb all of the training information that the trainer has provided, and the trainer also has a limited amount of time to explain the training materials to the trainee. The second is technical issues. Some of them stated that they now employ outdated or insufficient equipment, which makes it difficult to produce good training. The training facility is not suitable for holding training sessions, which brings us to our next technical concern. Sometimes, the location might have been too small or difficult to reach. The location will improve the training and development program if it is suitable.

Training costs come in third. Because training is expensive, many responders find it inconvenient to try to enroll. Fourth is the information provided. Sometimes they believe it was too general or difficult to comprehend. They advise the teacher to choose a less complicated technique so that the student will comprehend the materials. The researcher also questioned the respondents about the difficulties involved in running or participating in training and development programs. Most of them respond and improve. Gaining new abilities after leading or participating in a training program is undoubtedly difficult for both the trainer and the trainee. The majority of them choose on-the-job training as the last option after performing a questionnaire and interview to determine which type of training is seen to be more successful and efficient. They particularly enjoy on-the-job training because they believe they can apply their newly acquired information to their jobs right away and can consult the facilitator if they run into any problems.

Training and development program are one efficient solution that can address most of the problems above. The researcher's surveys and interviews have helped to support this information. Training enhances motivation, knowledge, and abilities. Long-term training and development programs can boost sales and even help MSMEs grow as businesses. There are a few factors to take into consideration in order to run an efficient training and development program. These factors should be taken into account based on the secondary data, interview, and questionnaire:

- Overcome technical obstacles: the trainer must ensure that the setting can support good training, that the materials being presented are pertinent to the subjects, and that the equipment is adequate.
- Conduct training output evaluation in relation to employee productivity to determine whether the training is sufficient to address skill and employee development concerns. In addition, training needs to be repeated several times rather than being completed in one sitting to be as successful as possible.
- Overcome problems with motivation: The training program must be engaging to keep participants motivated and enthusiastic, and participants can encourage or support one another.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, a well-designed training program can increase a company's employees' skills and knowledge, which has the potential to significantly increase production and efficiency. A thorough description of these programs can help businesses achieve the objectives they have set for themselves by clearly defining for employees the benefits they may anticipate from them. The majority of interviewees and questionnaire respondents chose on-the-job training over off-the-job training because it is flexible, cost-effective, easy to obtain, and most importantly, it fosters teamwork. Another factor is that on-the-job training programs focus on teaching essential skills initially, enabling new workers to help out with basic tasks right away.

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